

Design of Critical Experiments Involving Graphite Elements with the New IPEN/MB-01 Plate-Type Core

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ABSTRACT

A series of critical experiments were designed using SCALE KENO-VI. These experiments involve the use of characterized graphite elements in the new plate-type core of the IPEN/MB-01 reactor using fuel elements consisting of U₃Si₂-Al enriched to 19.75 wt % ²³⁵U. Eleven configurations with different graphite quantities are considered, each of which produces distinct effects on neutron fluxes and offers opportunities to analyze varying sensitivities to k_{eff} in the system. The analysis indicates that these experiments can be performed with acceptably low k_{eff} uncertainties considering an adequate characterization of the graphite elements to be used. Sensitivity results obtained using SCALE TSUNAMI calculations show that the experiments have a notable k_{eff} sensitivity coefficient to graphite, and the preliminary uncertainty analysis shows that the use of the graphite elements should not significantly affect the overall experimental uncertainty. These experiments will be useful for both criticality safety and nuclear data validation as a result of using the well-characterized graphite elements. The 11 designed configurations serve as a basis for the final design, and fewer configurations will be executed. Once executed, these critical experiments will be evaluated and submitted for publication in the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) Handbook, supporting the DOE/NRC Collaboration for Criticality Safety Support for Commercial-Scale HALEU Fuel Cycles and Transportation (DNCSH) project goal.

Keywords: HALEU fuel, ICSBEP, critical experiment, SCALE, Monte Carlo

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper serves as a brief description and summary for ORNL/TM-2025/3915 [1], a report published in 2025 by Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) titled “Design of Critical Experiments Involving Graphite Elements at the IPEN/MB-01 Plate-Type Core.” The purpose of this report is to describe the design of a series of critical experiments that include 19.75% enriched ²³⁵U and graphite, fulfilling one of the goals of the DOE/NRC Collaboration for Criticality Safety Support for Commercial-Scale HALEU Fuel Cycles and Transportation (DNCSH) project [2] highlighted in Experiments and Analysis Work Package (EAW) #1 [3] (i.e., the availability of nuclear criticality benchmarks to validate the transport of high-assay low-enriched uranium [HALEU] fuel for licensing purposes) [4]. The focus of EAW #1, introduced by a public workshop [5], was requesting critical experiment benchmarks to be published in the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) Handbook [6] from five different areas, including 10%–20% enriched ²³⁵U and advanced reactor moderators such as graphite. EAW #1 also included a nuclear data validation component, and graphite needs integral experiments to help validate the recent ENDF/B nuclear data releases, such as ENDF/B-VIII.1 [7].

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Because of its low neutron absorption, high thermal conductivity, and resistance to high temperatures and radiation damage, graphite plays a key role in nuclear reactor design as both a neutron moderator and a structural material. Graphite's performance—which depends on manufacturing processes that determine characteristics such as grain size, purity, binder content, density, and porosity—affects key properties such as mechanical strength and thermal behavior. Ongoing research aims to better characterize these properties to support next-generation reactor designs and life-extension programs [8]. Porosity is especially significant because it influences mechanical integrity, oxidation resistance, and neutron moderation, with radiation causing dimensional changes as pore structures evolve [9]. Accurately predicting and controlling both initial and radiation-induced porosity is therefore crucial for the long-term safety and reliability of reactor graphite components. In this context, a new research campaign is proposed at the IPEN/MB-01 zero-power research reactor in São Paulo, Brazil, to establish new experimental benchmarks. The project intends to integrate graphite inserts into the reactor's core or reflector regions to study the material's behavior in a critical experiment.

The IPEN/MB-01 reactor, which operated for 30 years with UO_2 fuel rods enriched to 4.3 wt % ^{235}U and was used in several published benchmarks in the ICSBEP and International Reactor Physics Evaluation Project (IRPhEP) [10] Handbooks, was recently upgraded to a plate-type fuel configuration that features a 4×5 core of 19 $\text{U}_3\text{Si}_2\text{-Al}$ fuel elements enriched to 19.75 wt % ^{235}U . The new configuration, shown in Figures 1 and 2, includes a removable aluminum block at core position B-3 and uses four hafnium plates (labeled BC1 through BC4) for reactivity control and safety. Radial reflection is provided by heavy water (D_2O) in four tanks, and the core is immersed in a light-water (H_2O) tank. The reactor utilizes two classes of fuel elements: standard (with plates mechanically attached) and dismantlable (for flexible handling and precise ^{235}U critical mass determination). Dismountable elements are placed at the core's corner positions. Each standard fuel element consists of 21 fuel plates separated by light water. A detailed description and evaluation of the reactor in its nominal configuration (without graphite) is set to be published in an upcoming ICSBEP evaluation as ICT-007 [11].

Figure 1. IPEN/MB-01 new plate-type core.

Figure 2. IPEN/MB-01 new plate-type core, selected as the cover of the 2022/2023 IRPhEP Handbook.

The objectives of this experimental design are as follows:

- Quantify changes in reactivity associated with the introduction of graphite in the core.
- Describe different critical configuration candidates, including graphite, for the execution of the experiment.
- Evaluate the sensitivity coefficient of k_{eff} to different isotopes, including graphite, to prove the usefulness of the experiment for both criticality safety and nuclear data validation.
- Measure spectral modifications in the neutron flux due to moderation and scattering effects.
- Assess and evaluate the effect of graphite porosity and grade on these parameters.
- Evaluate added experimental uncertainty due to the use of graphite inserts in the core.

The core modifications to obtain the designed critical configurations will be taking place in core positions A-1, D-1, A-5, D-5, and B-3. All configurations were designed using the preliminary benchmark model of ICT-007 and the SCALE 6.3.2 [12] CSAS6 sequence (KENO-VI) with the ENDF/B-VIII.0 [13] nuclear data library. Only an excerpt of the analysis from ORNL/TM-2025/3915 is shown in this paper. For more information, refer to the published report [1].

2. PROPOSED EXPERIMENT CONCEPT

The proposed 11 critical configurations are summarized in Table 1. The graphite elements to be used are modeled as a $70 \times 3.85 \times 3.85$ cm cuboid of 1.713 g/cm^3 density with a surrounding layer of 0.2 cm thick aluminum, as shown in Figure 3. The cases can be considered as two sets: The first set is configurations 1 to 6, and the second set is configurations 7 to 11. The first set starts with a base case without graphite and involves the subsequent addition of modeled graphite elements in the four corners of the lattice and in the center, as shown in Figure 4. Note that case 6 involves removing the center fuel element to replace it with a graphite element. In the second set (cases 7–11), the four corners of the lattice are fuel elements, and the central graphite element is cut axially into four different parts of equal height and subsequently added to the core, as shown in Figure 5. In all 11 configurations, criticality is achieved by simultaneously adjusting the four control plate heights. Adding more graphite elements in the core and changing their locations allows a broad range of parameters to be tested, including changes in the neutron spectrum within both the assembly and the graphite, as well as the sensitivity of the system's k_{eff} to changes in graphite contents and distribution. To fit with the bottom aluminum matrix plate of the IPEN/MB-01 plate-type core, the graphite elements will also be attached to a bottom aluminum nozzle. The number of cases in the planned experiment execution and ICSBEP evaluation will be lower than 11. Case selection will be performed at a later stage in the project after refined discussions with IPEN/MB-01 operating staff.

Table 1. Proposed experiment configurations.

Configuration number	Configuration description	Number of graphite elements	Number of fuel elements
1	Base case 1 , 16 fuel elements with empty corners, no graphite	0	16
2 to 5	From case 1, addition of one graphite element in each corner and in the center (A-1, D-1, A-5, D-5)	1 to 4	16
6	From case 5, replacement of the central fuel element B-3 location by a graphite element	5	15
7	Base case 2 , 19 fuel elements with empty central B-4 location, no graphite	0	19
8 to 11	From case 7, addition of one to four graphite element parts on the bottom of B-3 location	0.25 to 1	19

Figure 3. Graphite element representation.

Figure 4. Top views of proposed configurations 3 (left) and 6 (right).

Figure 5. Top view (left) and side view (right) of proposed configurations 8 (top) and 11 (bottom).

3. GRAPHITE CHARACTERIZATION PLANS

Graphite's performance in nuclear reactors is strongly dependent on physical and chemical characteristics, including purity, crystallographic structure, porosity, and isotopic composition. For the integral benchmark experiments planned at the IPEN/MB-01 research reactor, careful selection and characterization of graphite material are essential to ensuring reproducibility and alignment with ICSBEP standards.

The graphite selected for the IPEN/MB-01 experiments is of a nuclear-grade type, commonly referred to as high-purity, fine-grain graphite, pile grade A. This grade was chosen for its low impurity content (particularly boron and other neutron-absorbing elements), high structural integrity, and uniform microstructure. Nuclear-grade graphite typically meets or exceeds the ASTM D7219 [14] and ISO 12677 [15] standards for nuclear applications, ensuring consistent performance in neutron transport simulations. Key properties of the selected graphite grade include carbon contents > 99.9% by weight, ash content < 100 ppm, density of 1.713 g/cm³, and grain size < 0.1 mm.

Porosity is among the most critical of the parameters that govern graphite behavior in reactor physics applications. It influences the material's effective density, moderation ratio, and thermal conductivity, all of which can affect neutron economy in a benchmark setup. Open porosity contributes to variation in bulk density and affects how neutrons scatter and slow down within the material. Closed porosity, although less influential on moderation, can affect heat transfer and structural performance under irradiation. Usual values for graphite porosity are as follows [8-9]:

- Total (open and closed) porosity: ~18%–22%
- Open porosity: ~15%–18%
- Pore size distribution: submicrometer to tens of micrometers

Accounting for porosity is not necessary for benchmark modeling, but it is beneficial to study it. The effective macroscopic cross sections for scattering and absorption must reflect the reduced atomic number density due to the void fraction. Additionally, the heterogeneity introduced by porosity could affect the interpretation of experimental results, particularly in fine-structure flux measurements [16-17]. The design of the graphite elements is currently in progress at IPEN. The design maintains the same external dimensions as the standard fuel element and is secured in the matrix plate using a solid bottom nozzle. The graphite is encased within a thin aluminum jacket, and the assembly (including both top and bottom closures) is sealed in a compact, robust manner. The planned dimensions of the graphite element are shown in Figure 3. IPEN is conducting a comprehensive graphite characterization campaign. The graphite density has already been measured, yielding a value of 1.713 g/cm³, which is consistent with design expectations. Ongoing analyses include the determination of porosity and grain size using a SkyScan 1275 X-ray microtomography system [1].

In addition, impurity content—particularly for elements with high neutron absorption cross sections, such as boron and cadmium—will be quantified using conventional chemical analysis techniques. These measurements are essential for ensuring the graphite's suitability for nuclear applications, for accurate modeling in benchmark experiments, and for deriving an experimental uncertainty due to the graphite insertion in the core. Finally, the dimensions of the graphite element and related aluminum components (e.g., sleeve, holder, handle) will also be carefully measured, and their uncertainties will be evaluated. Accurate modeling of graphite in reactor simulations is essential for predicting neutron moderation, reflection, and thermalization behavior. In the context of the integral benchmark experiments planned at IPEN/MB-01, the fidelity of graphite modeling directly affects the interpretation of neutron flux spectra, reaction rates, and effective multiplication factors.

In continuous energy (CE) Monte Carlo simulations (e.g., MCNP [18] or SCALE CE-KENO), the graphite geometry is modeled explicitly so the neutron tracking considers the detailed interactions with the carbon atoms. In deterministic calculations, graphite is modeled using groupwise cross sections derived from consistent processing (e.g., NJOY [19] or AMPX [20]), with resonance self-shielding and anisotropic scattering carefully treated. A critical component of graphite modeling is the thermal scattering law (TSL), which governs how neutrons interact with bound atoms at thermal energies. The TSL data for graphite are usually based on evaluations such as ENDF/B-VIII.0 [13], ENDF/B-VIII.1 [7], JEFF-3.3 [21], or JENDL-5 [22], which provide $S(\alpha,\beta)$ libraries for crystalline carbon at various

temperatures (e.g., 293.6 K, 600 K). For benchmark fidelity, the inclusion of $S(\alpha, \beta)$ data is essential when temperatures and neutron spectra are thermal. The planned experiments at IPEN/MB-01 will use graphite as a moderator or reflector in a well-characterized configuration to evaluate thermalization effects in the neutron field. This is particularly relevant for validating criticality safety validation computational models containing graphite, and also for validating transport models and group constant generation methods in graphite-containing systems [16-17]. By using well characterized graphite with known grade and detailed porosity, the benchmark experiment ensures traceability and supports high-fidelity modeling using deterministic and stochastic transport codes. This also aligns with best practices for integral benchmark experiments submitted to international databases, such as ICSBEP.

4. ADDITIONAL DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

Additional characteristics of the proposed critical configurations are described in ORNL/TM-2025/3915, including neutron flux calculation comparisons between configurations with and without graphite blocks inserted, a sensitivity study performed with SCALE TSUNAMI that shows the most impactful isotopes and reactions in the system, and a preliminary study of the effect of the insertion of the graphite elements on the overall benchmark uncertainty. The main conclusions of these studies are as follows:

Flux comparisons: When the graphite block is inserted into the B-3 location and in the four corners from configurations 1–6, the peak neutron flux is shifted to the right of the central graphite block. The flux is concentrated in the empty water channel (B-3) for configuration 7, but when the graphite block is inserted into the same position, the flux is shifted again to the right of the block. These profiles demonstrate the differences in moderators/scattering material influence on the flux for the reactor system, showing that the proposed critical configurations will be useful for graphite validation.

Sensitivity study: The sensitivity study used the TSUNAMI-3D sequence of SCALE with ENDF/B-VIII.0 data to calculate k_{eff} sensitivity coefficients for various mixtures, elements, and isotopes in different IPEN/MB-01 reactor configurations. Among several designs that maximize graphite's effect on k_{eff} , four configurations (1, 6, 7, and 11) were chosen for the sensitivity analysis: configuration 1 without graphite, configuration 6 with a graphite block at B-3 and four outer corner graphite blocks, configuration 7 with fuel plates replacing graphite at B-3, and configuration 11 with a graphite block at B-3 and fuel plates at the corners. Direct perturbation calculations validated the TSUNAMI-3D results. In configurations without graphite (1 and 7), the highest k_{eff} sensitivity coefficients are linked to ^{235}U in fuel plates and ^1H in the light-water moderator with ~ 0.23 for ^{235}U in configuration 7, and ~ 0.23 for ^1H in configuration 1. Adding graphite—as done in configurations 11 and 6—results in noticeable increases in the k_{eff} sensitivity coefficient for graphite, for a maximum of 0.025 in configuration 6. Looking at the sensitivity per energy, the highest contributions correspond to the fast energy region and around 1 eV near the ^{235}U resonance energy.

Experiment uncertainty: The experimental uncertainties differ from those described in ICT-007 only by the inclusion of graphite elements and aluminum holders. The primary uncertainty comes from the dimensions and composition of the graphite elements, whose effects on k_{eff} are added in quadrature to the uncertainties already listed in ICT-007. One uncertainty that could not yet be evaluated is the uniformity of the graphite along all axes; preliminary measurements gave a density of 1.713 g/cm³ and 12% porosity. More extensive tests are planned. The uncertainties are quantified by multiplying sensitivity values from KENO-VI perturbation calculations by their respective uncertainties. The key points for each parameter are as follows:

- Graphite density: Uncertainty is taken as half of the last significant digit in accordance with the ICSBEP guide [23]; it is expected to be lower than 0.0015 g/cm³ once fully evaluated. The evaluated delta k_{eff} is negligible.
- Graphite element width/height and aluminum cladding thickness: An uncertainty of 0.01 cm is used based on prior IPEN/MB-01 ICSBEP evaluations, representing an estimated upper bound. The evaluated delta k_{eff} is 25 pcm due to the width uncertainty.
- Boron impurities in graphite: With no direct measurements yet, graphite is modeled with 6 ppm of boron based on ASTM D7219-19 [14], and an uncertainty of 0.5 ppm is assigned using both

the ICSBEP and ASTM guidelines. The evaluated delta k_{eff} is 35 pcm maximum in configuration 6 with the highest number of graphite elements.

- Graphite porosity: The total, open, and closed porosity of samples of the graphite elements will be studied to infer on the homogeneity of the elements and further refine the graphite elements benchmark modeling.

This approach ensures that all significant uncertainty factors are considered and will be refined as more precise measurements become available. Overall, the experimental uncertainty, estimated around 100 pcm in a base case without graphite, should not significantly increase due to the addition of the graphite elements, as other parameters such as the fuel plate pitch will have a higher weight when used in a quadratic sum.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The critical experiments designed in this work include the use of characterized graphite elements in the new plate-type core of the IPEN/MB-01 reactor. Eleven different configurations are considered. These configurations have different amounts of graphite and different corresponding effects on neutron fluxes, providing opportunities to analyze different sensitivities to k_{eff} in the system. The analysis shows that such experiments can be performed with acceptably low k_{eff} uncertainties considering an adequate characterization of the graphite elements to be used. The sensitivity results obtained using TSUNAMI calculations show that the experiments have a notable k_{eff} graphite sensitivity coefficient. Additionally, the neutron flux calculations demonstrate that graphite shifts the system's neutron spectrum relative to water, adding more validation opportunities to these experiments. These experiments will be useful for both criticality safety and nuclear data validation because of the use of these characterized graphite elements. The eleven configurations designed serve as a basis for the final design, and fewer configurations will be executed.

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